

Aristea Africana Blousuurkanol

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Group: Monocot

Size: 5 cm in height

Distribution:

Widespread across the
Western Cape

Importance:

Aristea africana represents a key taxonomic group within the genus *Aristea*, contributing to broader representation of this lineage within the highly diverse family Iridaceae. As a widespread Cape species, its genome offers significant research value, with potential to provide insights into adaptation, speciation, and evolutionary relationships within the genus. The species is also of conservation significance, highlighting its value as a model for evolutionary and ecological research.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 12.53 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 31.99 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.51 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 87.8%, Duplicated: 12%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 25 557.78 kilobases

Contig number: 162

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